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Transformation of ichnofabric variables and its generated curves: the ichnological modus operandi in paleoenvironmental analysis

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Abstract

A large of ichnofabric variables (*e.g.* bioturbation index, ichnodiversity, ethology, penetration depth, and burrow diameter) from 381 ichnofabric units has been collected in Miocene deltaic setting in Lower Kutai Basin. The principal component analysis (PCA) was used to transform a large ichnofabric variables into its main, representative features by projection of the data into a two-dimensional presentation. The findings of this research are (1) principal components (*i.e.* PC-1 and PC-2) which is composed by ichnofabric variables, (2) principal component curves. PC-1 is made up of bioturbation index, ichnodiversity, ethology, penetration depth, and maximum burrow diameter with

different magnitude. Conversely, PC-2 is constituted by the penetration depth (PD) and maximum burrow diameter (Dm). The transformation of ichnofabric variables generate the curves that demonstrate the paleodepositional environment such as colonization window, biological factor, paleoenvironmental conditions and dynamics.

Keywords: ichnofabric variables, principal component analysis, bioturbation index, ichnodiversity, ethology, penetration depth, burrow diameter

Introduction

Intricate interrelationship between the environmental conditions are indicated in nature. That could be

Figure 1 Geological map (left) and research site (right) (modified from Hall and Nichols, 2002; McClay, et al. 2000).

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including positive and negative feed-back loops (*e.g.* see figure 8 in Savrda and Bottjer, 1994). Ichnofabric variable may be an indicator of one or more paleoenvironmental conditions (see *e.g.* Rhoads, 1975; Goldring, 1964; Howard, 1975; Savrda and Bottjer, 1991).

However, each ichnofabric variables are partly mentioned during paleoenvironmental studies without regard potential interrelationship between each ichnofabric variables (see in Arifullah, et al. 2016a and Savrda and Bottjer, 1987, 1991). For example, in fact the organism size (*i.e.* represented by burrow diameter) has a positive correlation with penetration depth (see Levinton, 1977; Reise, 1979). In other words, the biological factors should be considered in ichnological interpretation.

Since, ichnofabric variables are an indicator of a complex feed back relationship, the ecological hierarchies concept (see Wu and Loucks, 1995) is adopted. Consequently, it may be applied in ichnological approach. A composite ichnofabric variables with varying in magnitude may constitute the higher hierarchy one. Thus, this approach avoids the partial paleoenvironmental interpretation based on each ichnofabric variables but transformed to more integrated one.

Materials And Methods

Research site

The research area is located in Samarinda, Indonesia (Figure 1). The geology of this area comprises Balikpapan Formation, deposited within the Kutai Basin. This basin is bordered to the north by Sangkulirang strike-slip fault, to the south by Paternoster strike-slip fault. To the west, the basin is bordered by highly deformed and uplifted Paleogene sediments and Cretaceous metasediments that make up the Central Kalimantan Mountains.

The Kutai Basin is open to the east by the Makassar Strait. Moreover, Samarinda Area was depocenter during the Miocene (Moss and Chambers, 1999) that interpreted as a deltaic setting (*e.g.* Allen and Chambers, et al. 1998; Bachtar, 2004; Arifullah, 2005).

Table 1. An example of the represented by four ichnofabric units of 381 total population and its original measurement of ichnofabric variables.

N	Ichnofabric Units	PD (cm)	Dm (cm)	BI	ID	NE
1	Op-07	30	1.5	3	2	1
2	Ch-03	75	0.3	3	2	2
3	Pa-03	28	1.5	2	3	1
4	Ch-04	50	0.5	1	1	1
N = 381						

Table 2. An example normal distribution value that converted from table 1.

N	Ichnofabric Units	PD	Dm	BI	ID	NE
1	Op-07	0.97	0.57	0.65	0.59	0.28
2	Ch-03	1.00	0.13	0.65	0.59	0.30
3	Pa-03	0.96	0.57	0.35	0.88	0.00
4	Ch-04	1.00	0.18	0.12	0.24	0.00
N = 381						

Table 3. An example of condensation of multi-dimension data into its main, representative features projection of the data into a two-dimensional from table 2.

N	Ichnofabric Units	PC-1	PC-2	PC-3	PC-4	PC-5
1	Op-07	0.4	0.2	0.3	-0.2	0.1
2	Ch-03	0.2	-0.0	0.5	-0.5	0.1
3	Pa-03	0.3	0.2	0.5	0.1	-0.3
4	Ch-04	-0.4	0.3	0.5	-0.2	0.0
N = 381						

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A total of 4 outcrops, exposed in a 100's meter long lithological section was observed in Samarinda area along January to March 2016. The orientation of outcrops is NE-SW that coincidence with Kutai Basin structural trend (Figure 1). A detailed observation and description of ichnofabric units were conducted for every centimeter scale of beds. A total of 381 ichnofabric units were studied detailly. The main variables such as bioturbation index, ichnofossil diversity, the number of ethology, penetration depth, and maximum burrow diameter were collected of each ichnofabric units.

Ichnofabric analysis

Shortly, ichnofabric is sediment fabric as final product which resulted by interaction of tracemaker and sediment (see Ekdale and Bromley, 1983 in Ekdale, et al. 1991). Each sediment fabric can be defined as ichnofabric unit which represented by some ichnofabric variables, such as bioturbation index, ichnofossil diversity, the number of ethology, penetration depth, and burrow diameter (see Arifullah, et al., 2016a,b).

Bioturbation index (BI). Schemes for scaling the intensity of bioturbation are based on proportion of substrate obliteration that exhibited in each ichnofabric unit, and are presented as classes that developed by Taylor and Goldring (1993). The classes of bioturbation index are: BI 1 (1 - 5% of bedding obliterated); BI 2 (6 - 30%); BI 3 (31 - 60%); BI 4 (61 - 90%); BI 5 (91 - 99 %) and BI 6 (complete bioturbation: sediment reworking due to repeated overprinting).

Ichnodiversity (ID). It imply the ichnofossil variation in ichnofabric unit. Consequently, the ichnofossil identification is critical. The systematics criteria for ichnofossil identification had been formulated by Knaust (2012). That are including orientation, branched or not, shape, lining or not lining and characteristic of burrow fill. An orientation burrow is classified into subhorizontal (tunnel), sub-vertical (shaft) and complex (see "box work" in Ekdale, et al. 1984) which determined by the orientation of the bedding surface.

The number of ethology (NE). Post ichnodiversity identification, the number of ethology can be resolved.

Figure 2 The scree plot of PC's eigenvalue and the percent of variance explained by each component is shown decreasing order. PC-1 = 42.38 %; PC-2 = 23.30 %; PC-3 = 17.10 %; PC-4 = 14.23 % ; PC-5 = 3.00 %. In this case, the sum of PC-1 and PC-2 could be a representative of two-dimensional presentation.

Figure 3 PC-1 has positive correlation with all ichnofabric variables that contribute with different magnitude. As a note, penetration depth (PD) indicates the lowest contributor in the PC-1.

Figure 4 PC-2 has positive correlation with penetration depth (PD) and maximum burrow diameter (Dm), conversely has negative correlation with ichnodiversity (ID) and number of ethology (NE).

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Table 4. The summary statistics of the sample population (N = 381).

Summary Statistics	PD (cm)	Dm (cm)	BI	ID	NE
N	381	381	381	381	381
Min	1.00	0.10	1.00	1.00	1.00
Max	75.00	5.00	6.00	7.00	4.00
Sum	4861	508.1	950	672	504
Mean	12.76	1.33	2.49	1.76	1.32
Std. error	0.46	0.05	0.07	0.05	0.03
Variance	79.79	0.83	1.65	1.15	0.31
Stand. dev	8.93	0.91	1.28	1.07	0.56
Median	10.00	1.00	2.00	1.00	1.00
25 prcentil	8.00	0.80	1.00	1.00	1.00
75 prcentil	15.00	1.80	3.00	2.00	2.00
Skewness	2.20	1.42	0.76	1.58	1.61
Kurtosis	7.97	2.04	0.13	2.58	2.15

N = number of population; Min = smallest value; Max = biggest value; Std. error = standard error; Stand. dev = standard deviation.

Each ichnofossil is suggested at least one ethological class. Seilacher, (1964); Frey and Seilacher, (1980) had create the ethological classification, such as resting (cubichnia), dwelling (domichnia), locomotion (rapichnia), grazing (paschichnia), deposit feeding (fodonichnia), farming (agricrichnia), escape (fugichnia) and equilibrium (equilibrichnia). However, the ethology can be determined after a detailed description of the ichnofossil. If an ichnofabric unit exhibit dwelling (domichnia) and deposit feeding (fodonichnia), then it is mean at least two ethology are developed in the unit.

Penetration depth (PD). Many taxa live at or just beneath the sediment water interface, while others live for several centimeters below the surface, and still others live in decimeters and even metres within the sediment (Bromley and Ekdale, 1986). How to recognize the deeper and shallower penetration of tracefossil in the rock record has been outlined by Bromley (1996), Kotake (1993), Savrda and Bottjer (1987), Wetzel and Aigner (1986). Furthermore,

composite ichnofabric where initial ichnofabric unit overprinted by later ichnofabric unit should be approached by analyzing cross-cutting relationship among burrow (see Ekdale and Bromley, 1986; Wetzel and Aigner, 1986; Savrda and Bottjer, 1987, 1991).

Maximum Burrow diameter (Dm). Burrow diameter indicates tracemaker size which occupied the burrow. Before measurement the burrow diameter, it is critical to recognize the general burrow structure such as the existing of burrow lining (see Ekdale, et al. 1984). *Ophiomorpha* and *Paleophycus* are the examples which burrow lining had been constructed by tracemaker, but *Planolites* and *Thalassinoides* had been not. The true burrow diameter is the measurement diameter of burrow fill exclude burrow lining.

Statistical Analysis

To study the general size of bioturbation effect, statistical analysis were performed. Each ichnofabric variables in the 381 ichnofabric units were observed. As a result, the big picture ichnofabric variables are achieved. PAST-3 was used to perform both statistical and principal component analyses.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA).

PCA, is a multivariate statistical technique which uses orthogonal transformation to convert a set of correlated variables into a set of orthogonal, uncorrelated axes called principal components (e.g. Gotelli and Ellison 2004). Since ichnofabric is dealing with paleoecology and using multivariate datasets (i.e. bioturbation index, ichnofossil diversity, the number of ethology, penetration depth, and burrow diameter), this is why PCA is an attractive used method (see the application in Van Der Zwaan and Jorissen, 1991).

PCA enables condensation of data on a multivariate phenomenon into its main, representative features by projection of the data into a two-dimensional presentation. The two created resource axes are independent, and although they reduce the number of dimensions (i.e. the original data is complex), they maintain the original relationship between the variables significantly. PCA requires normal data distribution, consequently the original data (Table 1) would be

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transformed to a normal distribution value (Table 2) that exhibit the dimension less.

PC curve shapes

The consequences of principal component analysis are resulting new scores of each ichnofabric units which called PC-1 and PC-2 scores (Table 3). That score is dimension less that possible to plot as ichnofabric curves as like as electrofacies log. The shapes are adopted from general using terminology in log analysis, such as an irregular, symmetrical, bell, funnel and cylindrical (see Cant, 1992). That shape is analysed in superposition of the rock record. PC-1 and PC-2 scores are depicted in red and blue line colours.

Results

Summary statistics

Summary statistics of ichnofabric variables within 381 ichnofabric units are shown in the table. 4. In the table, the outstanding result is shown by the penetration depth (PD). It shows the biggest standard deviation. Its mean, the value of PD is diverged than other one of ichnofabric variables.

PC and its ichnofabric variables composition

Principal Component-1 (PC-1). The eigenvalue percentage of variance is 42.38% (Figure 2). All ichnofabric variables (*i.e.* BI, ichnodiversity, the number of ethology, maximum burrow diameter and penetration depth) give the contribution to the PC-1 with different proportion. Anyway, in the figure 3, the proportion indicates normal distribution and has a positive correlation with PC-1. However, BI and ichnodiversity are the first and second most loading in PC-1. In addition, penetration depth is the lowest contributor in PC-1. The increasing of BI is followed by increasing the ichnodiversity.

Principal Component-2 (PC-2). The estimation of eigenvalue percentage of variance is lower than PC-1 and indicated with 23.30 % (Figure 2). The figure 4, the penetration depth and maximum burrow diameter values are the first and second most loading in the PC-2 that has a positive correlation with the PC-2. The increasing of penetration depth is accompanied by

increasing the burrow diameter. Conversely, bioturbation index, ichnodiversity and number of ethology has negative correlation. That means these values increasing with the decreasing of PC-2. Volume of total percentage of variance (*i.e.* PC-1 + PC-2) is 65.68 %.

Generated PC curves

The consequences of principal component analysis are resulting in the dimension less of new scores of each ichnofabric units that called PC-1 and PC-2 scores. The an example of oscillated PC curve (Figure 5) indicates the switching of ichnofabric variables during depositional process with different magnitude of the return interval.

In addition, the terminology of irregular, symmetrical, bell, funnel and cylindrical shapes. However, the depositional environment meaning of that curves are still scrutinized. That exhibits the decrease, increase and constant upward with both PC scores. The terminology of BI, ichnodiversity, penetration depth and burrow diameter increasing or decreasing upward can be employed.

PC-1 curves. The maximum and minimum PC-1 scores is 0.99 and -0.6. If PC-1 score lower than -0.6, then it is exhibit the barren (no bioturbation indicated, *i.e.* BI:0). Refer to the preceding explanation, then PC-1 curves symbolize the BI and ichnodiversity.

PC-2 curves. The maximum and minimum of PC-2 scores are 0.69 and -0.7. If PC-2 score lower than -0.7, then it is exhibit the barren (no bioturbation indicated, *i.e.* BI:0). As mention before, that PC-2 stands for penetration depth and burrow diameter.

Discussion

The interplay of fluvial, tidal, wave (*e.g.* Allen and Chambers, 1998; Bachtiar, 2004; Arifullah, 2005) in deltaic setting result the multidimensional paleoenvironmental conditions which reflected by the intricate ichnofabric variables (*i.e.* BI, ichnodiversity, penetration depth and burrow diameter). However, this paper do not interpret separately the paleoenvironmental conditions based on each ichnofabric variable. It should

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keep in mind that PC-1 and PC-2 are uncorrelated things but may equal hierarchy in paleoenvironmental system.

Colonization window

The time available for colonization by trace maker (see Pollard et al. 1993; Taylor, et al. 2003) may be the major factor in ichnofossil formation. The existing any kind of ichnofabric variables with different magnitude (Figure 3) may suggest the enough time for colonization is available and supported by other paleoenvironmental conditions (e.g. paleosalinity, paleotemperature and paleoxygen).

Biological factors

The biological clue of PC-2 (Figure 4, e.g. penetration depth and burrow diameter) may be resolved by the idea of Levinton (1977) who had made one think of the animal may shift their level of vertical partition during ontogeny. Adult animal feed at deeper tier with growth and reproduction seasonally than juveniles (see Reise, 1979) or avoiding the predator (see Bromley, 1996). In turn of those facts are only adult animal (i.e. deposit feeder) has the ability to penetrate deeply for surviving and the BI score will be higher in the deeper tier.

Small or juvenile organisms are usually relatively more tolerant of low oxygen (e.g. see Shumway, et al. 1983). Consequently, it can be reflected in a reduction of burrow diameters with declining oxygen (Aller, 1982; Savrda and Bottjer, 1987). However, it is not necessary the existence of smaller burrow diameter suggests the lower oxygenation.

The other clue (i.e. negative correlation penetration depth-burrow diameter versus ichnodiversity-number ethology) may suggest the number of adapted strategy will reduce follow the reduction oxygen content in the deeper tier (see Bromley 1996).

Paleoenvironmental conditions

The PC-2 (Figure 4, e.g. penetration depth and burrow diameter) is employed to resolve the interpretation specific paleoenvironmental conditions (e.g. paleosalinity and paleotemperature). Salinity generally only becomes an important limiting factor in marginal marine environments which are brackish or hypersaline

(Brenchley and Harper, 1998). In relation to behavioral responses of burrowing organisms, the steep gradients in salinity and temperature are similar; therefore, these two variables are considered together (Rhoads, 1975). Since deep borrowing species experience less salinity (c.f. salinity fluctuation between neap and spring tides in Sanders, et al. 1965) and thermal variation (e.g. Johnson 1965) than near surface organisms, then penetration depth data may be valuable in paleosalinity and paleotemperature interpretation.

Based on “biological factor” above, it may be mentioned that only adult animal can survive with the paleotemperature and paleosalinity fluctuation. The small or juvenile organisms are extinct potentially.

Paleoenvironmental dynamics

The shapes of PC curves may imply the paleoecological succession. For example, bell and funnel shapes of PC-1 scores suggest the colonization window is decrease and increase. In applied sedimentology, PC-1 (e.g. BI) will show the situation of the decrease and increase biogenic reworking (see “contest” physical versus biological processes or a combination of those in Howard, 1975). In the same way, PC-2 trend suggest biological factor is increase or decrease.

PC-1 and PC-2 curve do not necessary switch in positive correlation, even the negative correlation is indicated (see Figure 5). The scrutinizing of the ichnofabric curves (e.g. irregular shapes and correlation in Figure 5) and integrated it with ichnofacies and lithofacies resolve the paleo-depositional environment (e.g. “tidal rhythmites” in Figure 5).

Conclusions

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is useful tool enabling ordination of ichnofabric variables in ichnological study. If PC-1 and PC-2 are the higher hierarchy than ichnofabric variables, consequently the interpretation of paleoenvironmental condition of PC-1 and PC-2 may be more discriminating and the major paleoenvironmental condition can be shown up.

This ichnofabric methods can be applied to other basin analysis. The composition of ichnofabric variables on

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PC-1 and PC-2 and the curves style may be resulted. Before interpretation of the result, it is critical to identify the scale of any depositional environment within the broader context of regional geology.

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